

Supplementary information for: COBREXA 2

Authors of COBREXA 2

1 S1 Elaborated constraint systems

2 S1.1 Incremental construction of resource-balanced models

3 Enzyme-balanced FBA construction

4 FBA models are composed of a stoichiometric matrix, \mathbf{S} , enforcing mass balance on a vector of
5 the modeled fluxes, v , which are usually directionally constrained through lower bounds \mathbf{v}_{LB} and
6 upper bounds \mathbf{v}_{UB} . A typical FBA representation is shown in Supplementary System 1: The system
7 is formulated as an optimization problem that maximizes the biomass objective function (μ); the
8 optimum is then the highest-yield solution [1].

9 Enzyme kinetics computation requires a ‘unidirectional’ view of the reactions in the model; we
10 therefore split the (possibly bidirectional) variables in the model into their unidirectional counterparts
11 using Supplementary System 2.

12 Enzyme-constrained FBA (ec-FBA) models extend Supplementary System 2 with enzyme kinetics,
13 derived mainly from turnover numbers (k_{cat} s) and proteome capacity limitations [2, 3, 4]. ec-FBA
14 models explicitly account for the protein cost, associated with a metabolic flux. A complete ec-FBA
15 formulation is shown as Supplementary System 3.

16 In Supplementary System 3 we explicitly make room multiple capacity bounds $E_{1,\dots,n}$ where the
17 enzymes are selected and weighted by corresponding vectors $m_{1,\dots,n}$.

18 Simplified RBA

19 Resource balance analysis (RBA) seeks to extend ec-FBA models by incorporating gene expression
20 (transcription and translation) into the model formulation [5, 6]. Simplified RBA (sRBA), as presented
21 in Supplementary System 5 partially shares this goal, but only accounts for translation (ribosomes),
22 energy costs associated with protein synthesis, and biomass component growth dilution.

23 Since we are interested in a chemostat-like simulation, we fix μ and minimize the resource parsimony
24 objective: $\sum_j e_j \cdot m_j + m_k \cdot \sum_k r_k$ (which is equivalent to minimizing the L1 norm of the protein
25 content of the model).

26 Implementation of Supplementary System 5 in COBREXA 2 is available in the supplementary
27 code archive at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14606532>, file `scripts/03_srba.jl`, function
28 `with_srba_constraints`, totaling 90 lines of commented code.

29 A usecase-independent implementation of sRBA is available as a reusable example notebook in
30 COBREXA.jl documentation, or via <https://cobrex.github.io/COBREXA.jl/v2.7.0/examples/07a-srba/>.

$\max \mu$	maximize growth
$\mu = \mathbf{v}^T \mathbf{c}$	objective function
$\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{0}$	mass balance
$\mathbf{v}_{\text{LB}} \leq \mathbf{v}$	lower flux bounds
$\mathbf{v}_{\text{UB}} \geq \mathbf{v}$	upper flux bounds

Supplementary System 1: Flux balance analysis as a linear program. The variables in this program are the fluxes, \mathbf{v} and the biomass objective function, μ . In COBREXA, this system is generated via `flux_balance_constraints`.

$\mathbf{u}^+ \geq 0$	forward fluxes
$\mathbf{u}^- \geq 0$	reverse fluxes
$\mathbf{u}^+ \leq \mathbf{v}_{\text{UB}}$	forward flux bounds
$\mathbf{u}^- \leq -\mathbf{v}_{\text{LB}}$	reverse flux bounds
$\mathbf{u}^+ - \mathbf{u}^- = \mathbf{v}$	directionality balance

Supplementary System 2: Unidirectional reaction variable system as an extension of Supplementary System 1. The additional variables here are the unidirectional fluxes in the forward, and reverse directions, \mathbf{u}^+ , \mathbf{u}^- . Notably, the system allows the reactions to 'run' in both forward and reverse direction at once. In COBREXA, this system is generated via `sign_split_constraints` and several related functions.

$\mathbf{e} \geq 0$	isozyme amounts
$\sum_{i \in \text{FWDISOS}(r)} \mathbf{k}_{\text{cat } i} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i \geq \mathbf{u}_r^+ $	$(\forall r \in R_e)$ forward catalysis capability of isozymes
$\sum_{i \in \text{REVISOS}(r)} \mathbf{k}_{\text{cat } i} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i \geq \mathbf{u}_r^- $	$(\forall r \in R_e)$ reverse catalysis capability of isozymes
$(\forall i) \quad \mathbf{e}^T \mathbf{m}_i \leq E_i$	capacity limitations

Supplementary System 3: ec-FBA as constraints that extend the FBA with unidirectional reactions (Supplementary System 2). The new variables stand for enzyme concentrations \mathbf{e} , and the grouped enzyme capacity bounds E_i (each i thus specifies a group of enzymes to be bounded). In COBREXA, this system is generated via `enzyme_constraints`.

$E_{\text{mem}} = 0.2 \cdot \sum_i E_i$	membrane-to-total protein mass ratio
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Supplementary System 4: Additional ec-FBA constraint to keep the membrane protein capacity in biologically expectable range. In COBREXA, this system is generated via `equal_value_constraint` and adding and scaling of values in constraint trees. (Index of E_{mem} labels one of the general indices i of E in Supplementary System 3).

$\max \mu'$ $\mathbf{0} = (\mathbf{S}' \quad \mathbf{b}) \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{v}' \\ \mu' \end{pmatrix}$ $\mathbf{b}_i = \begin{cases} - \left(\sum_j e_j \cdot N_i(e_j) + \sum_k r_k \cdot N_i(r_k) \right) & \text{if } i \in \text{amino acids} \\ \mathbf{S}_{i, \text{biomass}} + \nu_i \left(\sum_j e_j \cdot N_*(e_j) + \sum_k r_k \cdot N_*(r_k) \right) & \text{if } i \in \begin{cases} \text{ATP} \\ \text{ADP} \\ \text{H}_2\text{O} \\ \text{H}^+ \\ \text{Pi} \end{cases} \\ \mathbf{S}_{i, \text{biomass}} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ $\mu' \cdot e_i = \frac{k_r}{N_*(e_i)} \cdot r_i \quad (\forall i \in \text{proteins})$ $\mu' \cdot \sum_i r_i = \frac{k_r}{N_*(r_r)} \cdot r_r$ $E_{\text{mem}} \geq \sum_i m_i \cdot e_i$ $E_{\text{total}} \geq \sum_i m_i \cdot e_i + \sum_i m_i \cdot r_i$	<p>maximize resource-based growth</p> <p>metabolite and biomass balance</p> <p>biomass composition</p> <p>enzyme translation</p> <p>ribosome translation</p> <p>enzyme mass on membrane</p> <p>total protein capacity</p>
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Supplementary System 5: sRBA as constraints that extend the ec-FBA (Supplementary System 3). In the system, the biomass function decomposition to components (\mathbf{b}_i) ensures that non-amino acid and energy metabolites are produced at the same rate as the ec-FBA model, and that the energy and amino-acid cost of the transcription scales with the amount of enzymes required to catalyze the metabolic flux. The total number of amino acids in a molecule x is counted by $N_*(x)$, and the number of amino acids of type y in a molecule x is counted by $N_y(x)$. P is the ATP cost of polymerization of an amino acid into a protein (by default, $P = 4.2$). k_r is the ribosome translation rate is (by default, $k_r = 12$). The ATP requirement for growth is adjusted according to the amount of ATP is needed to produce the enzymes, \mathbf{e} , and the ribosomes, \mathbf{r} . The ATP hydrolysis equation is used to modify the amount of energy currency metabolites in the original biomass function, $\text{ATP} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{ADP} + \text{PO}_4 + \text{H}^+$ — here, ν_i marks the stoichiometry of the metabolites in this reaction. Notably, the sRBA model is bilinear in μ and $(\mathbf{e}, \mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v})$. Enough ribosomes must be made to produce all the enzymes, as well as the ribosomes necessary to produce the enzymes.

32 **S1.2 Constraint systems for enzyme-constrained communities**

33 Supplementary Figure S1 is provided as an illustration of the situation in a co-culture of auxotrophic
34 organisms.

35 ec-cFBA models used in the manuscript are illustrated in Supplementary Figure S1. The formula-
36 tion of the ec-cFBA problem is listed in Supplementary System 6.

37 Implementation of Supplementary System 6 in COBREXA 2 is available in the supplementary code
38 archive at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14606532>, file `scripts/common/auxotrophe_community.jl`,
39 function `auxotrophe_community`, totaling 71 lines of commented code.

40 A usecase-independent implementation of ec-cFBA is also available as a reusable example note-
41 book in COBREXA.jl documentation, or via [https://cobrexa.github.io/COBREXA.jl/v2.7.0/](https://cobrexa.github.io/COBREXA.jl/v2.7.0/examples/07b-community-ecfba/)
42 `examples/07b-community-ecfba/`.

Figure S1: Illustration of mutually auxotrophic *E. coli* co-culture. ΔmetA cannot produce methionine, ΔilvA cannot produce isoleucine. The strains can grow only when co-cultured.

$\max c$		maximize the community growth
$\mathbf{a}_i \geq 0$	$(\forall i)$	individual community member abundances
$\sum_i \mathbf{a}_i = 1$		abundances sum to 1
$\sum_i \mathbf{v}_{ix} a_i = \mathbf{v}_{c,x}$	$(\forall x \in X)$	community exchange balance
$\mu_i = c$	$(\forall i)$	community growth balance

Supplementary System 6: Enzyme-constrained 2-member community FBA (ec-cFBA) as a linear program. The problem includes several instances of Supplementary System 3 with all variables indexed by the community member index i (i.e., stoichiometry of the i -th member is \mathbf{S}_i and the internal flux in i -th member is \mathbf{v}_i). For simplicity, we assume that the set of exchange reaction indexes X is the same in all community members; realistic software implementations will instead select the reactions by a pre-established shared identifier scheme. In addition to the variables defined previously, a_i represents the abundance of species i . Environmental exchange is modeled by $v_{c,x}$ for metabolite x . In COBREXA, this system is generated via `interface_constraints`; suitable interfaces are obtained from `flux_balance_constraints`.

43 S2 Construction and interpretation of use-case models

44 S2.1 Incremental construction of an iML1515 resource-balanced model

45 To demonstrate the construction of complex models from simple building blocks, we incrementally
46 constructed an example genome-scale enzyme- and translation-constrained model of *E. coli*. Our
47 construction is based on a conventional FBA model of a mass-balanced reaction system, iML1515 [7].
48 Initially, we created a system of unidirectional reactions atop the original model, and added constraints
49 that incorporate enzyme turnover numbers (k_{cat} s), and proteome capacity limitations [2, 3], which
50 explicitly account for the protein cost of a given metabolic flux. Crucially, since modeling overflow
51 metabolism requires at least two active bounds [8], we added both a membrane bound, and a total
52 proteome density bound to the model. The exact form of the model is elaborated in Section S1.1. For
53 the parametrization of enzymatic constraints, we used *in silico*-estimated enzyme turnover numbers [9]
54 for all presented experiments, together with a total enzyme capacity bound of $0.55 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{g}_{\text{DW}}}$, and membrane
55 enzyme capacity bound $0.11 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{g}_{\text{DW}}}$ (i.e., the amount of membrane enzymes is bounded to 20% of the
56 total enzyme amount).

57 Because protein synthesis is a major biosynthetic cost in bacteria that outweighs both transcription
58 and translation energy requirements [10], we reasoned that a simplified variant of Resource Balance
59 Analysis (RBA) [5, 6], only taking into account ribosomes, ATP, and amino acid requirements of
60 protein synthesis, would be sufficient to mechanistically model overflow metabolism. Through the
61 text, we label this simplified RBA as sRBA. For sRBA models in this work, we set the ribosome
62 translation rate to 12 amino acids per second, and the polymerization cost to 4.2 ATP per amino
63 acid. Additionally, the L1 norm of proteins and ribosomes is minimized at each growth rate, in order
64 to ensure a sufficiently unique solution from the possibly under-determined constraint system.

65 In this formulation, sRBA is a straightforward extension of enzyme constrained FBA (ec-FBA)
66 models. We note that the full RBA problem formulation that simulates the transcription and
67 replication machinery may be constructed as another extension of this model. As a major benefit
68 compared to full RBA, the parameters required for sRBA model construction are relatively well-
69 determined and easy to collect from public databases. The exact definition of the sRBA model is
70 provided in Section S1.1.

71 Discussion of results obtained from iML1515 sRBA model

72 The protein fraction of cellular dry mass varies by less than 10% across a range of growth conditions
73 (Supplementary Figure S2) [11]. This density constraint has been used to provide a mechanistic
74 explanation for overflow metabolism [12]. In essence, the density limitation forces the cell into a
75 trade-off between devoting resources to catabolism and anabolism: During slower growth regimes, the
76 cells favor higher yield but proteomically costlier respiration (with kinetically slower, bigger enzymes),
77 while at higher growth rates, fermentative metabolism is also used (in the case of *E. coli*, this results
78 in aerobic acetate production). Fermentative ATP generation is kinetically faster, requires smaller
79 enzymes, but ATP yield is lower than from respiration. Additionally, since ribosomes are needed to
80 produce both enzymes *and* the ribosomes themselves, and their translation rate is limited, increased
81 ribosome concentrations are required to support higher growth rates [13, 14]. In turn, this leaves
82 even less space for large enzymes, and forms the basis for the resource partition trade-off observed in
83 bacteria, which leads to overflow metabolism [15].

84 Expectably, we encode the constant density observation into ec-FBA models via a single constraint
85 that restricts the total proteome density to a chosen constant. Additionally, we use a secondary
86 membrane capacity bound to reflect the physical constraint of limited membrane space. Assuming
87 this bound structure causes the onset of overflow metabolism to be controlled by the membrane
88 capacity bound [17, 18], which is in contrast to simpler resource allocation models that only posit a

Figure S2: Protein density across a range of culturing conditions of *E. coli*. Dots represent individual experimental measurements [11]. Mean value with 10% relative tolerance is highlighted in green on the right side.

Figure S3: Fraction of cytosolic and membrane-bound proteins measured in different growing conditions of *E. coli*. Points represent experimental measurements [16], lines represent least-squares regression in each compartment. Slope of either of the regression fits is not significantly different from 0.

89 total capacity bound [2, 19]. This assumption is further supported by recent quantitative proteomics
90 measurements, which revealed the mass ratio between cytosolic and membrane-bound proteins as
91 relatively constant over a wide range of growth conditions (Supplementary Figure S3) [16]. In total,
92 we use these assumptions to set two capacity bounds in the ec-FBA models: a total protein ($0.55 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{g}_{\text{DW}}}$),
93 and a membrane capacity bound (20% of the total protein capacity).

94 Simulations of the constructed *E. coli* ec-FBA model in COBREXA 2 (Supplementary Figure S6)
95 show that when a membrane protein that is ‘useless’ in the context of glucose-driven growth (e.g.
96 WT *lacY* or the engineered proton-leaking *lacY*) is over-expressed, less space remains for transporters
97 and respiratory membrane-bound complexes, causing the earlier onset of overflow metabolism. On
98 the contrary, over-expressing a ‘useless’ cytosolic protein (*lacZ*) shows no effect. That contradicts
99 recent experimental results, which showed that over-expressing either of *lacZ* and the proton-leaking
100 *lacY* caused the earlier onset of overflow metabolism.

101 Naturally, we hypothesized that extending the ec-FBA model with further resource allocation
102 constraints would capture the observed phenotypic behavior, and extended the ec-FBA model with
103 sRBA constraints that account for ribosomes that occupy additional cytosolic space, and for the
104 amino-acid and ATP cost of protein polymerization.

105 The *E. coli* sRBA model improved the predictive accuracy of our simulations over ec-FBA, showing
106 that over-expression of *lacZ* also leads to the earlier onset of overflow metabolism. We additionally
107 observed that the membrane bound is still a driver of this result, as an over-expression of *lacZ* requires
108 more ATP to be produced (due to protein polymerization costs), which increases the amount of
109 energy generating membrane proteins at each growth rate relative to the WT simulation. Thus, the
110 earlier onset of the overflow metabolism is caused indirectly by hitting the capacity limitation at the
111 membrane.

112 Possible interpretations of the results from sRBA simulations

113 Basan et al. [15] did not find evidence that membrane capacity would determine the switch to the
114 overflow metabolism when attempting to over-express WT *lacY*, which contradicts our results, where
115 WT *lacY* causes the switch. At the same time, Wagner et al. [20] found evidence of this effect for
116 several other (GFP-fused, WT) membrane proteins. We hypothesize that this apparent contradiction
117 could be explained by the difficulties of over-expressing membrane proteins.

118 Further experiments might thus be necessary to elucidate the effect: mainly, the fraction of the
119 proteome taken by the over-expressed *lacY* should be determined experimentally (these measurements
120 were not reported by Basan et al. [15]). On the other hand, over-expressed *lacZ* was measured
121 at more than 8% of the proteome, representing substantial metabolic stress (even in terms of
122 ATP polymerization costs). This way, our simulations lend support to the ‘membrane real estate
123 hypothesis’ [17, 18] for explaining overflow metabolism, but the results are not dispositive.

124 S2.2 Parameter choices for the sRBA model

125 To parameterize each example model, we gathered the enzyme turnover numbers directly from [9], the
126 enzyme sub-unit stoichiometry from Uniprot [21] and the Complex Portal [22], and the translation
127 rate from [23].

128 We opted to use representative values for parameters that have growth rate dependent effects (e.g.
129 translation rate of 12 amino acids per second), and average values specific constants like the ribosome
130 molar mass (2700 kDa¹), amino acid composition of the ribosome (7459 amino acids per ribosome²),

¹<https://bionumbers.hms.harvard.edu/bionumber.aspx?id=100118&ver=10&trm=e+coli+ribosome+molar+mass&org=>

²<https://bionumbers.hms.harvard.edu/bionumber.aspx?id=101175>

131 ATP protein polymerization cost (4.2 ATP per amino acid³), etc. Links to all data sources together
132 with cleaned extracted data files are reported in the source code repository. The parameters were
133 used as gathered, with no parameter fitting procedure involved.

134 We additionally summarize the sensitivity of the constructed model to the translation rate
135 parameter (k_r), which seemed to be the most sensitive to perturbations: In Figure 1C in main text,
136 we compare of the ribosome mass fractions using the translation rate of 12 amino acids per second (a
137 representative average value) against 9 and 17 amino acids per seconds (the minimum and maximum
138 measured value reported by Dai et al.) [23]. Notably, the average value recapitulates the experimental
139 data well, and the mass fractions seem to differ between the average and extreme parametrization only
140 by a constant relative factor. We did not observe any substantial impact of changing the translation
141 rate on the metabolic flux (Supplementary Figure S6).

142 S2.3 Construction of enzyme-constrained communities

143 To further demonstrate the versatility of COBREXA 2, we constructed enzyme-constrained community
144 models of interacting *E. coli* mutants.

145 These mutants were modeled as auxotrophic for 14 specific amino acids, using single-gene deletions
146 in the relevant biosynthetic pathways, as has been done experimentally [24, 25]. The auxotrophic
147 models were additionally constrained by enzyme kinetic and capacity constraints (analogous to the
148 *E. coli* extension specified in Section S1.1, but only with the total enzyme capacity bound). Individual
149 models were connected via their exchange reactions, with exchange fluxes weighted by the abundance
150 of the mutant, and the biomass production rates of each mutant model was constrained to the same
151 value, effectively creating a community growth rate as in the cFBA method [26]. Additionally, the
152 mutants were allowed to share the knocked-out amino acids with each other. To avoid the bilinearity
153 of the cFBA model (in abundances and fluxes), we solved the problem multiple times over a uniform
154 sample of possible abundances, and picked the solution with the maximum growth rate. The complete
155 constraint system construction is laid out in Section S1.2.

156 Discussion of results obtained from iML1515 enzyme-constrained auxotrophe community

157 Thus far, ec-FBA models have been mostly applied to single organisms [27], raising a question:
158 would adding enzyme constraints to community flux balance analysis (cFBA) models improve their
159 predictive accuracy? Previous attempts to answer this question made use of *ad hoc* constraints, e.g.
160 flux balance analysis with molecular crowding (FBAwMC) [28] was incorporated into a community
161 scale model of interacting bacteria, but this approach lacks the mechanistic details available when
162 using full enzyme constrained models (e.g. protein concentration predictions cannot be made [2]).
163 This drawback reflects the lack of parameters endemic to the field when FBAwMC was introduced
164 (*circa* 2007). More recently, quasi-resource allocation type constraints were added to community flux
165 balance models through the incorporation of an L1 bound on total reaction flux in each community
166 member [29]. This approach also eschews important details, like enzyme speed and size, which are
167 both physiologically important attributes, figuring prominently in ec-FBA.

168 Community-simulating extensions of FBA [30, 31] typically assume that each community member
169 grows at the same rate (otherwise the system is not at steady state), and metabolite flux exchange be-
170 tween members and their environments is weighted by the abundance of each microbe [26]. Previously,
171 data scarcity prevented adding enzyme bounds to genome-scale metabolic models, but this problem
172 has been attenuated by new *in silico* estimators, including machine learning [32], and omics-driven
173 parameter estimation techniques [33], allowing for the parametrization of ec-FBA models at community
174 scale.

³<https://bionumbers.hms.harvard.edu/bionumber.aspx?id=114971&ver=1&trm=ribosome+amino+acid&org=>

Figure S4: Comparison of growth predictions obtained for different compositions of ΔmetA – ΔilvA auxotroph *E. coli* community, using cFBA and ec-cFBA. In both simulations, the members were only allowed to exchange methionine and isoleucine. The vertical gray bar indicates the experimentally measured abundance [25].

175 We simulated mutually auxotrophic *E. coli* communities that were previously constructed experi-
 176 mentally by co-culturing mutants with complementary knockouts [24, 25]. Since each auxotrophic
 177 mutant lacks an essential gene for biosynthesis of a different amino acid [25], it is unable to grow
 178 in isolation, but may be rescued in a community where the amino acids may be exchanged with
 179 different mutants. However, the fundamental factors that determine the composition of the resultant
 180 communities are not well understood. Here, we hypothesize that each coupled community will adjust
 181 its abundance to grow as fast as possible, and investigate whether this optimality assumption holds
 182 by comparing measured abundance data to simulations using a classic cFBA, and enzyme-constrained
 183 cFBA (ec-cFBA).

184 First, we simulated a co-culture of ΔmetA (auxotrophic for methionine) and ΔilvA (auxotrophic for
 185 isoleucine) *E. coli* mutants. This pairing exhibits robust growth with a steady-state abundance of 20%
 186 ΔmetA , as established experimentally [25]. Supplementary Figure S4 compares the results obtained
 187 from ec-cFBA to conventional cFBA. Notably, with conventional cFBA the abundance of each member
 188 has only negligible effect on the community growth rate (up to extreme values), which is caused by
 189 the virtually identical metabolism of both members that can complement each other via zero-cost
 190 exchanges. This effect was previously prevented in simulations by incorporating non-mechanistic
 191 assumptions (i.e. a community MOMA-type simulation) that results in more realistic behavior [24].
 192 In contrast, results from ec-cFBA clearly show two distinct growth regimes as the abundance of
 193 ΔmetA changes, with a better defined optimum at the intersection of the regimes. Each regime
 194 corresponded to a specific partner limiting the growth of the community. In this particular case, the
 195 biosynthesis cost of the biomass of each mutant differ because of both the knockout and the necessity
 196 to supply amino acids to other community members at a rate that satiates the abundance-controlled
 197 demand, which ultimately determines the optimal community composition.

198 Fascinatingly, when we extended the same analysis to all co-culture communities that demonstrated
 199 significant growth (Figure 1D in main text), we observed that ec-cFBA offers substantially improved
 200 predictions over cFBA. The comparison included only amino-acid pairings that exhibit significant
 201 growth in experimental conditions (over 10-fold biomass increase over inoculum) [25]. ec-cFBA
 202 provided better predictions than cFBA in all cases (measured via centered-log-ratio-transformed
 203 compositional distance), improving the correlation with experimental data from 0.197 (cFBA) to
 204 0.453 (ec-cFBA). The ec-cFBA prediction compares well to the non-mechanistic (and non-steady
 205 state) approach used by Wintermute&Silver [24], who found a correlation of 0.42 across their dataset.
 206 Despite this, it is clear that both approaches are missing an important physiological constraint, since
 207 the predictive accuracy is relatively low. To improve, it might be necessary to incorporate either more
 208 precise regulatory effects or RBA-style constraints.

209 **S3 Supporting results**

210 Results from the simulation of 4-member community of *E. coli* mutants are summarized in Supple-
211 mentary Figure S5.

212 Full results obtained from comparison of ec-FBA and sRBA are shown in Supplementary Figure S6.
213 The reported results are a superset of ones in Figure 1B in main text.

Figure S5: Enzyme kinetics constraints are not sufficient to robustly reproduce the composition of a 4-member auxotrophic community of *E. coli* mutants. The plot is organized as slices of a 3-dimensional Aitchison simplex of the community compositions [34]. Simulation of $\Delta\text{metA}-\Delta\text{lysA}-\Delta\text{ilvA}-\Delta\text{thrC}$ community shows high variability in community compositions at near-optimal growth rates. The star represents the experimentally observed composition (ΔmetA 27%, ΔlysA 38%, ΔilvA 21%, ΔthrC 14%) [25].

Figure S6: Comparison of results obtained from ec-FBA and sRBA models. The figure interpretation is the same as for Figure 1B in the main text, but includes results from additional simulations from a model where lacY is over-expressed but not leaking protons (labeled lacY+) and sRBA models where translation rate is changed from 12 to 9 and 17 amino acids per second (labeled respectively WT+slow and WT+fast, corresponding to the same labels in Figure 1C in the main text). Results for WT and lacZ+ almost completely overlap in the ec-FBA models; the WT model is able to grow approximately 5% faster. Similarly, results for WT, WT+slow and WT+fast almost completely overlap in the sRBA models; as the main difference, WT+fast is able to grow approximately 2% faster than WT, which itself grows around 2% faster than WT+slow.

214 S4 Constraint trees

215 ConstraintTrees.jl is available as a separate package that we implemented to provide the constraint-
216 system representation for COBREXA 2. ConstraintTrees.jl is available from [https://github.com/](https://github.com/COBREXA/ConstraintTrees.jl)
217 [COBREXA/ConstraintTrees.jl](https://github.com/COBREXA/ConstraintTrees.jl) and from Julia package repositories. Stand-alone tutorial documenta-
218 tion for ConstraintTrees.jl is available from <https://cobrexa.github.io/ConstraintTrees.jl/>.

219 Supplementary Table S1 provides an overview of the “grammar” of constraint system manipulations
220 as implemented by ConstraintTrees.jl and COBREXA 2.

221 Constraint trees store a nested hierarchical structure of labeled constraints, organized into labeled
222 directories. Each constraint consists of a value part and an optional bound part. Semantically, the
223 value part defines a combination of variables in the system (typically a linear or quadratic one), and
224 the bound part describes a condition that the value must satisfy (typically that the value of the
225 combination of variables lies within a given interval). The labeled hierarchy carries no semantics in
226 the constraint system, and serves only for manipulation convenience.

227 Shown in the Supplementary Table S1, the labeling and selection operations provide a systematic
228 way to logically group any constraints, avoiding the need for name mangling (e.g., the oxygen exchange
229 in organism 2, seen in the extension operation example, does not need to be labeled with unstructured
230 identifier such as "member2_R_EX_o2_e" as common in other systems), and providing easy hierarchical
231 access to all system constituents. Intersection and extension are the central operations, respectively
232 representing intersection of feasible spaces of both constraint systems, and Cartesian product of the
233 feasible spaces of constraint systems. The extension operation prevents any intersection of the variable
234 sets of the given constraints, typically re-numbering the variable indexes of some of the operands,
235 yielding a system where both original systems coexist independently. The interfacing operation is
236 similar to extension, but additionally requires specification of the “module interfaces” (highlighted by
237 arrows in the figure) which are used to connect the modules together (i.e., the systems are no longer
238 independent in the result), and create an interface for the result that may be used for connecting more
239 systems. Optimizing the system w.r.t. a given objective produces a “value tree” where constraints
240 from the constraint tree are replaced by the evaluated combinations of the solved variables.

241 Notably, from the user perspective there is no difference between manipulating a constraint that
242 holds a variable and a constraint that holds a linear combination (a “derived value”) of the variables.
243 This property has two main implications:

- 244 • It abstracts the user from having to manage variable vector allocations, instead the variables
245 are typically allocated by using the extension (operator `+`) and interfacing (`join_interfaces`)
246 operations.
- 247 • It enables transparent interfacing of constraint systems: For example, a system that represents a
248 L2-parsimonious constraint can be built equivalently from the usual vector of flux-representing
249 variables, and from a vector of variable combinations that derive the values from other contents
250 of the model (such as sums of positive and negative reaction fluxes, and gene product capacity
251 vectors in enzyme-constrained models).

252 Internally, the variable objects in the constraint solver are allocated implicitly, based on the presence
253 of a referring index in the given constraint tree.

Operation name julia operation	Example use	Example result
Constraining values Constraint	<code>Constraint(x1, ≥ 0)</code>	<code>x1 ≥ 0</code>
Labeling ^	<code>reactions~PFK^ x1 ≥ 0</code>	<code>reactions</code> <code>PFK x1 ≥ 0</code>
Selection .[]	<code>exchanges</code> <code>O2 x23 ∈ [-10, 10]</code>	<code>x23 ∈ [-10, 10]</code>
Intersection *	<code>stoichiometry</code> <code>O2_e x23 - x85 = 0</code> * <code>exchanges</code> <code>O2 x85 ≥ -10</code>	<code>stoichiometry</code> <code>O2_e x23 - x85 = 0</code> <code>exchanges</code> <code>O2 x85 ≥ -10</code>
Extension +	<code>organism1</code> <code>O2_e x23 - x85 = 0</code> <code>CO2_e x15 - x68 = 0</code> ... + <code>organism2</code> <code>O2_e x23 - x85 = 0</code> <code>CO2_e x15 - x68 = 0</code> ...	<code>organism1</code> <code>O2_e x23 - x85 = 0</code> <code>CO2_e x15 - x68 = 0</code> ... <code>organism2</code> <code>O2_e x153 - x215 = 0</code> <code>CO2_e x145 - x198 = 0</code> ...
Module interfacing interface_constraints	<code>interf...</code> <code>organism1</code> <code>stoichiometry</code> <code>O2_e x23 - x85 = 0</code> ... <code>PFK KO x1 = 0</code> <code>exchanges</code> ← interface <code>O2 x85 ≥ -10</code> ... , <code>organism2</code> <code>stoichiometry</code> <code>O2_e x23 - x85 = 0</code> ... <code>ACALD KO x2 = 0</code> <code>exchanges</code> ← interface <code>O2 x85 ≥ -10</code> ...	<code>organism1</code> <code>stoichiometry</code> <code>O2_e x23 - x85 = 0</code> ... <code>PFK KO x1 = 0</code> <code>exchanges</code> <code>O2 x85 ≥ -10</code> ... <code>organism2</code> <code>stoichiometry</code> <code>O2_e x143 - x205 = 0</code> ... <code>ACALD KO x122 = 0</code> <code>exchanges</code> <code>O2 x205 ≥ -10</code> ... <code>interface_connection</code> <code>O2 x85 + x205 - x251 = 0</code> ... <code>exchanges</code> ← interface <code>O2 x251</code> ...
Optimization optimized_values	<code>optimized_values</code> (<code>organism</code> <code>exchanges</code> <code>O2 x85 ≤ 0</code> <code>CO2 x68 ≥ 0</code> <code>biomass x25 ≥ 0</code> ← maximize ...)	<code>organism</code> <code>exchanges</code> <code>O2 -5.2573</code> <code>CO2 7.3622</code> <code>biomass 0.873922</code> ...

Table S1: Main operations on constraint trees illustrated on examples.

254 Bibliography

- 255 [1] Timo R Maarleveld, Meike T Wortel, Brett G Olivier, Bas Teusink, and Frank J Bruggeman.
256 Interplay between constraints, objectives, and optimality for genome-scale stoichiometric models.
257 *PLoS computational biology*, 11(4):e1004166, 2015.
- 258 [2] Benjamín J Sánchez, Cheng Zhang, Avlant Nilsson, Petri-Jaan Lahtvee, Eduard J Kerkhoven,
259 and Jens Nielsen. Improving the phenotype predictions of a yeast genome-scale metabolic model
260 by incorporating enzymatic constraints. *Molecular systems biology*, 13(8):935, 2017.
- 261 [3] Roi Adadi, Benjamin Volkmer, Ron Milo, Matthias Heinemann, and Tomer Shlomi. Prediction
262 of microbial growth rate versus biomass yield by a metabolic network with kinetic parameters.
263 *PLoS computational biology*, 8(7):e1002575, 2012.
- 264 [4] Pavlos Stephanos Bekiaris and Steffen Klamt. Automatic construction of metabolic models with
265 enzyme constraints. *BMC bioinformatics*, 21:1–13, 2020.
- 266 [5] Douwe Molenaar, Rogier Van Berlo, Dick De Ridder, and Bas Teusink. Shifts in growth strategies
267 reflect tradeoffs in cellular economics. *Molecular systems biology*, 5(1):323, 2009.
- 268 [6] Anne Goelzer, Vincent Fromion, and Gérard Scorletti. Cell design in bacteria as a convex
269 optimization problem. *Automatica*, 47(6):1210–1218, 2011.
- 270 [7] Jonathan M Monk, Colton J Lloyd, Elizabeth Brunk, Nathan Mih, Anand Sastry, Zachary King,
271 Rikiya Takeuchi, Wataru Nomura, Zhen Zhang, Hirota Mori, et al. i ml1515, a knowledgebase
272 that computes escherichia coli traits. *Nature biotechnology*, 35(10):904–908, 2017.
- 273 [8] Daan H De Groot, Julia Lischke, Riccardo Muolo, Robert Planqué, Frank J Bruggeman, and Bas
274 Teusink. The common message of constraint-based optimization approaches: overflow metabolism
275 is caused by two growth-limiting constraints. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*, 77(3):441–453,
276 2020.
- 277 [9] David Heckmann, Anaamika Campeau, Colton J Lloyd, Patrick V Phaneuf, Ying Hefner, Marvic
278 Carrillo-Terrazas, Adam M Feist, David J Gonzalez, and Bernhard O Palsson. Kinetic profiling of
279 metabolic specialists demonstrates stability and consistency of in vivo enzyme turnover numbers.
280 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(37):23182–23190, 2020.
- 281 [10] Michael Lynch and Georgi K Marinov. The bioenergetic costs of a gene. *Proceedings of the
282 National Academy of Sciences*, 112(51):15690–15695, 2015.
- 283 [11] Markus Basan, Manlu Zhu, Xiongfeng Dai, Mya Warren, Daniel Sévin, Yi-Ping Wang, and
284 Terence Hwa. Inflating bacterial cells by increased protein synthesis. *Molecular systems biology*,
285 11(10):836, 2015.
- 286 [12] Matthew Scott, Carl W Gunderson, Eduard M Mateescu, Zhongge Zhang, and Terence Hwa.
287 Interdependence of cell growth and gene expression: origins and consequences. *Science*,
288 330(6007):1099–1102, 2010.

- 289 [13] Ron Milo. What is the total number of protein molecules per cell volume? a call to rethink some
290 published values. *Bioessays*, 35(12):1050–1055, 2013.
- 291 [14] Evert Bosdriesz, Douwe Molenaar, Bas Teusink, and Frank J Bruggeman. How fast-growing
292 bacteria robustly tune their ribosome concentration to approximate growth-rate maximization.
293 *The FEBS journal*, 282(10):2029–2044, 2015.
- 294 [15] Markus Basan, Sheng Hui, Hiroyuki Okano, Zhongge Zhang, Yang Shen, James R Williamson,
295 and Terence Hwa. Overflow metabolism in escherichia coli results from efficient proteome
296 allocation. *Nature*, 528(7580):99–104, 2015.
- 297 [16] Alexander Schmidt, Karl Kochanowski, Silke Vedelaar, Erik Ahrné, Benjamin Volkmer, Luciano
298 Callipo, Kevin Knoops, Manuel Bauer, Ruedi Aebersold, and Matthias Heinemann. The quanti-
299 tative and condition-dependent escherichia coli proteome. *Nature biotechnology*, 34(1):104–110,
300 2016.
- 301 [17] Kai Zhuang, Goutham N Vemuri, and Radhakrishnan Mahadevan. Economics of membrane
302 occupancy and respiro-fermentation. *Molecular systems biology*, 7(1):500, 2011.
- 303 [18] Mariola Szenk, Ken A Dill, and Adam MR de Graff. Why do fast-growing bacteria enter overflow
304 metabolism? testing the membrane real estate hypothesis. *Cell systems*, 5(2):95–104, 2017.
- 305 [19] Matteo Mori, Terence Hwa, Olivier C Martin, Andrea De Martino, and Enzo Marinari. Con-
306 strained allocation flux balance analysis. *PLoS computational biology*, 12(6):e1004913, 2016.
- 307 [20] Samuel Wagner, Louise Baars, A Jimmy Ytterberg, Anja Klussmeier, Claudia S Wagner, Olof
308 Nord, Per-Åke Nygren, Klaas J van Wijk, and Jan-Willem de Gier. Consequences of membrane
309 protein overexpression in escherichia coli. *Molecular & Cellular Proteomics*, 6(9):1527–1550,
310 2007.
- 311 [21] UniProt Consortium. Uniprot: a worldwide hub of protein knowledge. *Nucleic acids research*,
312 47(D1):D506–D515, 2019.
- 313 [22] Birgit HM Meldal, Livia Perfetto, Colin Combe, Tiago Lubiana, João Vitor Ferreira Cavalcante,
314 Hema Bye-A-Jee, Andra Waagmeester, Noemi Del-Toro, Anjali Shrivastava, Elisabeth Barrera,
315 et al. Complex portal 2022: new curation frontiers. *Nucleic acids research*, 50(D1):D578–D586,
316 2022.
- 317 [23] Xiongfeng Dai, Manlu Zhu, Mya Warren, Rohan Balakrishnan, Vadim Patsalo, Hiroyuki Okano,
318 James R Williamson, Kurt Fredrick, Yi-Ping Wang, and Terence Hwa. Reduction of translating
319 ribosomes enables escherichia coli to maintain elongation rates during slow growth. *Nature*
320 *microbiology*, 2(2):1–9, 2016.
- 321 [24] Edwin H Wintermute and Pamela A Silver. Emergent cooperation in microbial metabolism.
322 *Molecular systems biology*, 6(1):407, 2010.
- 323 [25] Michael T Mee, James J Collins, George M Church, and Harris H Wang. Syntrophic ex-
324 change in synthetic microbial communities. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*,
325 111(20):E2149–E2156, 2014.
- 326 [26] Willi Gottstein, Brett G Olivier, Frank J Bruggeman, and Bas Teusink. Constraint-based
327 stoichiometric modelling from single organisms to microbial communities. *Journal of the Royal*
328 *Society Interface*, 13(124):20160627, 2016.

- 329 [27] Iván Domenzain, Benjamín Sánchez, Mihail Anton, Eduard J Kerkhoven, Aarón Millán-Oropeza,
330 Céline Henry, Verena Siewers, John P Morrissey, Nikolaus Sonnenschein, and Jens Nielsen.
331 Reconstruction of a catalogue of genome-scale metabolic models with enzymatic constraints using
332 gecko 2.0. *Nature communications*, 13(1):3766, 2022.
- 333 [28] Qasim K Beg, Alexei Vazquez, Jason Ernst, Marcio A de Menezes, Ziv Bar-Joseph, A-L Barabási,
334 and Zoltán N Oltvai. Intracellular crowding defines the mode and sequence of substrate uptake
335 by escherichia coli and constrains its metabolic activity. *Proceedings of the National Academy of
336 Sciences*, 104(31):12663–12668, 2007.
- 337 [29] Minsuk Kim, Jaeyun Sung, and Nicholas Chia. Resource-allocation constraint governs structure
338 and function of microbial communities in metabolic modeling. *Metabolic Engineering*, 70:12–22,
339 2022.
- 340 [30] Siu Hung Joshua Chan, Margaret N Simons, and Costas D Maranas. Steadycom: predict-
341 ing microbial abundances while ensuring community stability. *PLoS computational biology*,
342 13(5):e1005539, 2017.
- 343 [31] Ruchir A Khandelwal, Brett G Olivier, Wilfred FM Röling, Bas Teusink, and Frank J Brugge-
344 man. Community flux balance analysis for microbial consortia at balanced growth. *PloS one*,
345 8(5):e64567, 2013.
- 346 [32] Alexander Kroll, Yvan Rousset, Xiao-Pan Hu, Nina A Liebrand, and Martin J Lercher. Turnover
347 number predictions for kinetically uncharacterized enzymes using machine and deep learning.
348 *Nature Communications*, 14(1):4139, 2023.
- 349 [33] St Elmo Wilken, Mathieu Besancon, Miroslav Kratochvíl, Chilperic Armel Foko Kuate, Christophe
350 Trefois, Wei Gu, and Oliver Ebenhöh. Interrogating the effect of enzyme kinetics on metabolism
351 using differentiable constraint-based models. *Metabolic engineering*, 74:72–82, 2022.
- 352 [34] Nicholas E. Hamilton and Michael Ferry. ggtern: Ternary diagrams using ggplot2. *Journal of
353 Statistical Software, Code Snippets*, 87(3):1–17, 2018.